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The comparison of leadership effectiveness of sport managers

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Abstract

Studies have shown that it is essential for organizational successful to have leadership effectiveness. This is applicable to all organizations as sport organizations. Therefore, the purpose of this research was to compare the leadership effectiveness of sport managers. The Statistical society was all managers of Sport and Young's Ministry, National Olympic committee, National Paralympics committee, National Olympic Academy, and Sport Federations (N=331). Base on Morgan table, 180 people were selected with stratified sampling method in this research. Researcher made Leadership effectiveness questionnaire was used to collect data. Data analysis was performed by one way ANOVA test and continuative LSD. The results showed that there was significant difference between leadership effectiveness in sport organizations of Iran ($p < 0/05$) and federations' managers had the most effectiveness. With respected to this results, it is necessary to execute programs to increase leadership effectiveness in organizations that had the minimum score of leadership effectiveness.

Keywords: Sport, Leadership Effectiveness, Manager

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